

3.08.A.T-04 Effects of Particle Size and Surface Charge Density on the Transport of Nanoplastic Particles Through Porous Media Under Unsaturated Conditions

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The use of plastic in the agricultural practices can lead to the formation of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) by fragmentation and degradation processes. The mobility and transport of these particles towards deeper soil horizons may be influenced by their physicochemical properties and the occurrence of unsaturated conditions. Modelling approaches investigating transport of MNPs through porous media under such conditions are relatively scarce. Therefore, in this study we explored the effects of particle size and surface charge density on the transport of polystyrene nanoplastic particles (PSNPs) through sand with the aim of quantifying such effects through numerical modelling techniques. PSNP infiltration experiments under unsaturated conditions were run in triplicate using an *ad hoc* designed system with glass columns. After a hydrochemical equilibration phase, fluorescent COOH-PSNPs (40 mg L^{-1}) were injected over the sand top surface at a flow rate of 0.5 mL min^{-1} . The effluent was collected every 30 min and PSNP concentrations were measured with an UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The hydraulic transport parameters of the sand were determined with a tracer test performed after PSNP infiltration. Additionally, PSNP transport through the porous media was simulated using ColloidFIT and COMSOL Multiphysics software. The DLVO theory was applied to calculate the total interaction energy between PSNPs and sand surface assisting in data interpretation. Results show that smaller particles reach higher plateau concentrations than larger particles indicating an influence of particle size on the mobility of PSNPs. Mass recovery percentages from each PSNPs confirm that larger particles tend to be more retained in the sand column. Preliminary modelling results show sorption-desorption rates that point at higher retention capacity for larger particles. According to calculated energy interaction forces, electrostatic repulsive forces between sand and PSNPs seem to be predominant under the experimental conditions, and particle retention should be more likely due to physical constraints in the sand pore spaces rather than chemical sorption processes. Regarding the surface charge density, a variation by a factor of 3 of this parameter does not influence the fate of PSNPs. Further experimental and numerical modelling is on-going and will help to gain further insights into MNP transport in porous media and the relevance of different processes on groundwater contamination.